

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MANYIKA****FIRST NAME: MORRIS****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

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QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In order to write effective academic essays, the following basic steps should be followed.

- Research the topic, Organize Ideas, Write, Reference, Edit and Hand In.**¹
- Research the topic, Write, Reference, Organize ideas, Edit and Hand In.
- Research the topic, Organize ideas, Reference, Hand in, Edit and Write.
- Organize ideas, Write, Hand in, Reference, Edit and Research the topic.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-12.

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2. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Explain why plagiarism *MUST* be avoided.

- It supports the writer of the of an essay to finish.
- It is wrong, unethical, serious academic offense and has serious consequences.²**
- It is acceptable in academics and has no consequences.
- It is another way of finding information.

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3. There are two main types of research; *pure* and *applied*. Contrast *Pure* and *Applied* Research.

- Pure research is mainly done purely without practice.
- Applied and Pure research are conducted at the same time.
- Applied research addresses conceptual problems and any direct practical consequences while pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.
- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences while applied addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.³**

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² Ibid., 7-12.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

4. In order to develop a constructive research argument, a researcher needs to engage sources of information. Which of the following is one of the uses secondary sources?

- Provide original” materials that provide you with the “raw” data.
- Provide data obtained through observation or experiment in many fields.
- Provide current research findings and find other points of view.**⁴
- Provide direct information on events.

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5. The notes style and author-date style are two commonly used citation styles. The author-date style is used when...

- You signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference.**⁵
- You signal that you have used a source by not placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference.
- You signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence.
- None of the above.

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⁴ Ibid., 36.

⁵ Ibid., 142-145.

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6. The Notes-Bibliography style plays a critical role in the referencing process. Which of the following is a correct way of writing a *Notes-Style* from multiple authors?

- ##. Author #1's First and Last Names and Author #2's Last and First Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Publisher's Name: Place of Publication, Date of Publication), page number.
- ##. Author #1's Last and First Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), page number.
- ##. Author #1's First and Last Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Page Number.⁶
- ##. Author #1's Last and First Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Publisher's Name: Place of Publication, Date of Publication), page number.

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7. Research Methodology is one of the main sections of a research proposal. One of the purposes of this section is to⁷

- Show how and in what ways you will go about conducting your study.⁷
- Show the literature reviewed to develop the proposal.
- Give a summary of the dissertation.
- Show the research findings, discussions, and conclusions.

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⁶ Ibid., 150.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, (London: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 208-209.

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8. The goal of theoretical research is to...

- Contribute new knowledge or extend current theory to a new area.**⁸
- Use knowledge to contribute directly to the understanding of a problem.
- Generate a solution for the problem.
- Conducting research.

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9. Abbreviations are used in the English language to help the readers.

- Emphasize the main point.
- Easily find the meanings of words
- Reduce the longevity of some words and quick access to items being meant.**⁹
- Increase the longevity of words, sentences, and paragraphs.

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10. What is a Style Guide?

- A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.**¹⁰
- A guide on how to develop styles of writing.
- A guide on how to reference.
- A list of styles on how to quote.

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⁸ Ibid., 240.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2021), 44.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 41.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. London: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

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European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. [European Commission, 2021](#).

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Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.